

YASA OF CHANGIZ KHAN

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Abstract: This article offers a roughly complete discussion of: previous Khorasan and the Afghanistan of present-day had come down the cruelty, and crucifixion of many commanders and presidors, one of them is changiz khan to have brought Afghanistan under his precept and Reign. This situation was an optimistic terrible and bloody one. Changiz khan has trodden his feet either on the page of the history of our country. It is the area where his gargantuan perfection was putting the people to the sword and killing civilians. He has come to Afghanistan and other territories. He brought on his illicit attack on our land/ Zone. It is absolutely bewildering that the people of Afghanistan had been looking for the mediation and was thirsty ever for standing alongside with the mediation; but this idea and prospection never turned into the reality. This mediation bringing was just like drawing a picture on the water. This land ever had the idea of peacekeeping but tragically not beheld it. Changiz and his army prosperously halted on Khorasan and pressurized to make afghans to acknowledge to him, concerning to their ideology and kept the attacks emanating.

It includes the key words: introduction, changiz khan's yasa, research methodology, findings, discussion, conclusion and encompasses the books that I have used as core references.

Key words: a short look on the life of Mughal, changiz khan, his yasa and endowments.

INTRODUCTION

Anyone who has carried through the cruelty, traced a special tactic for themselves. The subject, elected by me for my interrogation is about the changiz khan, who ruled himself in our land and did the cruelties in are never in a millions years admirable to humanity and under the very eyes of the humanical judgement. This was my view, what is yours?

Changiz khan concerning to his conquests is likewise to the Timor and askander and in putting the people to the death is identical to the Attila. Changiz in merits and behaviors is identical to Attila either, and in action how Attila said, "I had the power over the creature of god, and where my horse has trodden its feet; the grass won't be grown there over again." Changiz has acted upon his quotation in the Asia. One of the example of his brutality is on Fatima Khorasan, was the mother of gugak khan; she had been wiped up excessively and thrown her into the water when chaghatai khan got sick and mujadidin didn't treat him well so he had been shot and killed with his family. The matter is why changiz has moved on this regulation and what is the object of this law? The answer could be, that changiz khan had this anticipation of codifying this law just for setting his prehest prosperously in his family.

Literature Review

According to the abovesaid topic there is no information available in any articles, journals, books, internet websites, magazines and newspapers, the only information that I get from books is, that they recount changiz khan life was a lamenting one for the humanity and civilians. What I got is mostly from the books and alternative articles.

Materials and Methods

As far as the nature of this study concerns, qualitative research method suits best for this article. In analytic research, I could complete the major areas of this work by applying the principles of library research. In spite of the so-called data collection methods, I also interviewed the specialists and well-known about the life changiz khan. in this regard, Since the theme of the study is changiz khan's yasa, so I would like to draw your attention to the principal discussion.

Discussion

As far as the fact concerns; that there is really utilizable and incredible enough information to look at the life of changiz khan, his yasa and rule of his life this matter is either superlly discussed in the books of ahmad punahi, zhubal, and ghubar. they are harmonized about my research to be done in a really systematic and typical way. To be honest in this format of the of the article, the writers such as above mentioned are the ones who are coincident about research of mine.

A short look on the life of Mughal

Modeling of tamocheen's conference has handed in the alias of (changiz khan) to changiz khan which was empire in the overall Asia. This alias was set on him in 1306 AD and simultaneously another conference or assembly was compiled by qalamrukhan Mughal through the commanders of china, which was through the proposal of markiz (preceptor of china. The control of this tribe was in the (diwar bozarg). changiz khan has grabbed the conquests through apparent and religious credentials and believes of the people. Changiz khan had an unbeatable power which was admitted by his people and his other opponents on the overall the earth. With the whole reference and

preference, he had the super unbeatable potentiality on the insurgents, and controlling the tribe easily. Changiz khan had been presiding over those people, that they had been acceding no rules, tactics and tenets. These were the supine and stubborn people (changiz khan the powerful emperor on the whole universe, p. 120).

Mughal were the traders of skin and the hunters of the animals, the had been eating the meat and wearing the skinny the clothes. They weren't agricultural and farmers and living in a revolting way before changiz khan to turn out their chief.

His people were demarcated into alternative sections

- 1- Civilians, poor, and shepherds
- 2- The materialistic people
- 3- Those they had the one or two thousands farming animals

The justice of changiz khan

One of his commanders has been killing the people owing to the racist views.

He said, ' I broke into a home and wanted to kill the family at all. There was a baby, coming towards me and laughing at. I had a dagger in my hand that was put on his neck and wanted to cut his neck, but the baby conceived the dagger as the nipple of mom's boob. I really relented on him but emotion let me to leave him then I put him to the sword.

Changiz khan got extremely perplexed through story and order to suffocate that commander, by the way, it to be an enormous instance to the others. Judge Hameed Uddin pushing, that he was an epic member of the Khorasan, in the besets of Herat, he came under the slavery of changiz khan the compound was in consideration his experience, packed him off to the changiz khan. Changiz khan was posing from him about the prophets and sovereigns of Afghanistan/ Khorasan.

Changiz khan said, ' I paid back to Khwarazm shah, there could be no bigger retribution than that, he was a robber not a king, on the condition that he was a robber, so the people shouldn't have been put to the sword by him who were sent to him. Thus that compelled me to ask the declamation.

'Name of the exaltation remained from me or not?'

I said, 'assuming that changiz khan would give me the refugee I would respond him.'

Changiz told, ' I rid you off.'

I said, ' your name should have remained where the people remained alive, your army killed all the civilians. If your name remained alive, someone told that story to another person is whom?

I had been considering you the superlative alert, since you have no alertness. wherever Khwarazm shah has gone, I did execution there, king and people are more aggressive. He could have told my tale, ' changiz khan didn't suffice me, and it has caused me to flee (story of Mughal, pp. 74-75).

Sharafuddin Khwarazm has been traced the chief of supply's accumulation of Afghanistan. He had been teasing the people for grabbing the money from the people and assets, giving up the people and the other women the ghost and hanging them up. People were really gloomy and selling their babies to hand them over the payments of the captivity (Ghubar, p. 232).

believes of Mughals

They were endowing on the enchantment and superstitions. They weren't bathing in the winter and spring, not slaying the animals, and not wearing the gorgeous clothes in the sunny season. They had many cultures. Particularly they had the tall building, keeping women as the drudges, worshiping to the others and either believing on the god, having the long and long beard.

Changiz khan had this idea about his nation for instance: "the time come the ladies would become gorgeous under my power, putting on the superior clothes, eating the elite food, and mounting on the qualitative horses.

Changiz khan's yasa

Yasa means law, regulation and policy with amplifications yasa means the formality, bides regularities and doctrines. Especially this word is tacked on to changiz khan. This is the issue why changiz traced this legality? And what is the perfection of the legality? The perfection of this codification of this law is the succession of his army.

One of the idea of yasa

"After the five or ten years, assuming that any king will have come, the law of changiz khan mustn't be changed... the subsidization from the side of the god might come to them" changiz khan had been musing, and compiled the regulation which would be being acted upon by any of the sovereigns and other people, those people now have got nothing form the (yasa nama) of changiz khan (punahi, p. 81).

This law of yasa is for those people, that they are:

1-Perfectly emulating to changiz khan

2-Bringing the harmony in midst of the people and ejecting the disharmony from the nations

3-Packing out the castigation for the culprits and peculators

We have got no rubrics about the yasa now, is as much as little of that would be in the book of Rashid(history) here in this book he had been valuing the army, setting of the marines, balance of the creed, honoring the recluses, promoting the technology, security of roads of the commerce, supply of the goods, revering of the royals, breach of the inheritance, on perturbing of the menial women. (this dimension of his law wouldn't to be acted upon in the Muslim zones, mainly most of the times, many of the sovereigns and leaders even the people were impelled to abide by his rules, he has been a super superiors and cruel chief of captivated regions (Ghubar, p.190).

The laws and the doctrines, which were being utilized by the Mughal. The yasa nama of changiz khan was really being honored by the Mughal, no one could turn the rules down. Mughals were venerating to the holy Quran beside the yasa nama of the changiz khan (Ghubar, p. 94).

Submission of Mughal to the changiz khan, at all mandatory. After deriving the sovereignty of Mughal, he was being scarcely/ excessively revered by the Timor. Other zones were the zones of Timor ling and "tazook Timor" was either down the galvanization of the changiz khan (Punahi, p. 82).

Prospections of the yasa law

1- Law of women

2- In regulation of changiz khan, adultery and pilfering were forbidden. Anyone, who had been carrying through this crime was going to be chastised in regard of his criterion.

Law of blandness

Extensively in the reign, there was no peculation or theft. Even treasures in his time hadn't had any Key or locker, in his realm when the bird was to be abducted firstly, that was being attained. he was really humanical figure. Even the animals had the best collection and super clement herders (Changiz khan the power emperor on the whole universe p 125)

The emulation was there fully obligatorily father to his father, brother to older brother, posterity to parents, slaves to commanders, wives to husband and poor to rich. they were optimistically emulating to their owners and seniors. drinking wine was their enormous defect. changiz had been telling 'you ought to be lustful three times a month.

The regulation for the scout, lair lawyers and enchantment doers was to put to the death.

He really honored to the preachers, religious leaders. People were free in religious meeting and parties. He wasn't interrupting the people in any religious idea Muslim and Hindu. People could spin the life based on Sunnah and Hindu perspectives (changiz the valued power of the world/universe, p.122)

Changiz khan didn't prohibit the personal religious submission and the first law of changiz for religious issue was; humanity could worship to the all animal, earth and sky's. he had either the double god submitters.

Mughal people were really relenting and bland, even they were feeding the people in spite of any perfection /mission, they had no instance in doing the receptions to the guests.in the time of brokenness they were really contented, and they were superbly ahead of more folks in commemorating the parties and indulging the wedding music. None of the Mughals were doing the enhance in drinking the wine. They sufficed on their lust, neat of inspiration.

And bad the qualitative personality. they when pigs fly hinted them self-debarred then other in education and culture (Changiz khan the powerful emperor on the whole universe, p 125).

He was absolutely a provoking person. one of his rule was the Mughal ought to love each other and kill others. No one could escape from the battleground and keeping the fight lofty.

Some of the special laws of changiz;

Changiz hadn't been admitting another leader despite of himself his name and his posterity's names must be written by the golden pen and anyone, who called to him with the wrong/misnamed was going being chastised. All the conquered areas were his land (Punahi, p.83).

Conclusion and Findings

In conclusion, when the Mughals clasped on Khorasan, owing to their subduing, wildness, cruelty and over taming the people of Khorasan had no more than acknowledging to them in absolution. Changiz khan and his army were carrying through much cruelty on the folks and not retracting themselves from any sort of the terrific halts and crucifixion, thus the folks of Khorasan acknowledged to him. Changiz khan disgorged us nothing than mentioning his name in a really incorrigible gait and mood, and just having the horrible exploits form him on the page of history. The horrors were borne by the people of Khorasan many times and had them cracking again in the halts of Mughals and precepts of changiz khan. Controlling the globe, keeping their vigor, grandstanding and power over the universe, they made a law to put others to the sword. It was the reason, that Khwarazm shah blended with Mughal. The cruelty, halts on the downtrodden folks, sabotage, demolition and heroics were considered by them as their own religious allowance.

Result

As far as the discussion of this study concerns, it concludes that there is very credible and enough information to understand about the life the changiz khan, his yasa, policy, endowments and merits with the world, it was all about the backslash of changiz khan's life and a couple of events of his spirit, that we all would harmonize about. it is bootful to say that the life of changiz khan has handed us over another image of life. His crucifixion and brutality had been optimistically perilous concerning to the global rule of reigns. This was, what we are when pigs fly going to evoke in the history of sovereignty and presidencies. The finding of this research is that he has been scarcely horrible in his sovereignty and rule of living life. In spite of Lamenting the other nations, he had been terribly treating the folks of the subcontinent and other zones.

Recommendation

As far as I explored this topic from my knowledge, my request to other researchers is to keep their researches going, and extend their notion about the life of changiz khan and about this topic.

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